

Controlled Synthesis of Hierarchical Porous Ag_3PO_4 Microspheres through Natural Template for Photocatalytic Applications

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Abstract

Controlled synthesis of targeted morphologies in nanoscale is a challenging field for material chemists. Strategic methods would be required to obtain hierarchical porous semiconductors with specific morphologies or controlled porosities for surface applications. In the recent years, Ag_3PO_4 is considered as a useful material for semiconductor photocatalysis. There are many researchers attempted for the synthesis of these materials; however, Ag_3PO_4 having very high surface area is on the demand. In this work, we tried to achieve uniform hierarchical Ag_3PO_4 porous microspheres through natural bone glue (BG)-assisted one-step precipitation reaction at room temperature. We investigated the effect of supporting parameters (such as BG content, template constituents, temperature, reaction time, etc.) in tuning the morphology, porosity or size of Ag_3PO_4 . Photocatalytic capacity of the prepared material was established on the degradation of RhB and 2,4 DCP under visible light, which was found to be significantly better than other architectures. The method demonstrated would pave the way for development of porous hierarchical nanomaterials for various applications.

Scheme: Synthesis of hierarchical porous Ag_3PO_4 microspheres and their superior photocatalytic activity over other architectures.

Keywords: Bone glue, Rhodamine B, 2,4-Dichlorophenol, Photocatalysis, Visible light.

References

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